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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BCPC	Bulgarian Criminal Procedure Code
BE	Belgium
CCPC	Croatian Criminal Procedure Code
CY	Cyprus
EC	European Commission
ESO	European Supervision Order
EU	European Union
FI	Finland
GCPC	Greek Criminal Procedure Code
IE	Ireland
LU	Luxembourg
MS	Member States
NL	Netherlands
PCPC	Polish Criminal Procedure Code
PTD	Pre-trial detention
SCPC	Slovak Criminal Procedure Code
WHO	World Health Organization

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Executive Summary

The lack of use of non-custodial sentences is slowing down justice systems and overloading judges and prosecutors, forcing them to make quick verdicts. The list of existing alternative measures in countries of the European Union is lengthy, and yet very few alternatives are used. Accordingly, the purpose of the Policy Brief is to highlight the necessity of limiting the excessive usage of pre-trial detention and the adoption of alternative measures. These are the main proposed recommendations for reducing pre-trial detention in practice:

1. Further training of judges and prosecutors on alternative measures.
2. More cooperation between EU Member states is crucial in order to limit the discrepancy in practice currently present.
3. Cohesive time limits need to be set on all alternative measures, while being periodically revised.

1 Summary

The overuse of pre-trial detention is apparent in the over-crowdedness of European prisons. The lack of use of non-custodial measures is slowing down justice systems and overloading judges and prosecutors, forcing them to make quick verdicts. The list of existing alternative measures in countries of the European Union (EU) is lengthy, and yet very few alternatives are used. The European Commission (EC) has already warned EU Member States to use pre-trial detention (PTD) only as a measure of last resort, and not as a preventative measure.

These are just a few of conclusions that came from speaking with judges and lawyers from EU countries:

- Prisons are extremely overcrowded (205% capacity in a Croatian prison);
- Judges feel pressured to keep people in custody to prevent media criticism;
- Non-custodial measures such as electronic monitoring and bail have been proven successful, yet are barely used in practice;
- Judges aren't knowledgeable enough on alternatives and are accustomed to using pre-trial detention;
- EU Member States need to cooperate more when it comes to these matters.

Nevertheless, the existence of various alternative measures in EU countries allows for a solid foundation for a more common use of non-custodial measures in practice. Accordingly, the purpose of the Policy Brief is to highlight the necessity of limiting the excessive usage of PTD and the adoption of alternative measures. These are the proposed recommendations for reducing pre-trial detention in practice:

Further training of judges and prosecutors on alternative measures;

More cooperation between EU Member states is crucial in order to limit the discrepancy in practice currently present;

Cohesive time limits need to be set on all alternative measures, while being periodically revised.

1.1 The Overuse of Pre-trial Detention and Discrepancy in Practice

When it comes to the prison population, 22% of all prisoners in the EU are pre-trial detainees, with Croatia being one of the seven EU countries with the highest percentage of pre-trial detainees. Moreover, the average lengths of custody vary throughout Europe and are

unwarranted in their duration. For example, on average, pre-trial detention in Slovenia lasts for almost 13 months and 12 months in Greece (Apelblat, 2023). Some of the higher indicators of the average length of pre-trial detention (in months) were also found in Bulgaria (6.5), then Slovakia (3.9), while Poland and Croatia have not disclosed this information. The discrepancy in practice can be seen in the difference of maximum time limits for pre-trial detention throughout Europe, which vary from less than 1 year to more than 5 years. Six EU Member States don't have a maximum time limit for pre-trial detention put in place (BE, CY, FI, IE, LU, NL), while in Italy and Romania the limit for PTD is more than 5 years (Council of the European Union, 2022) (See Table 1.).

Table 1: Maximum time limit for pre-trial detention

Period	Consortium States
Less than 1 year	Slovakia
Between 1 and 2 years	Bulgaria, Greece, Poland
Between 2 and 5 years	Croatia

Sixteen prison administrations experienced a significant increase in their prison population rates from January 2022 to January 2023, leading with the Republic of Moldova (+52%). EU Member states experiencing the increase also include Croatia (+10%) and Bulgaria (+8.1%). Incarceration rates only fell substantially in a few countries, one of them being Greece (-5.2%) while they remained stable in 23 prison administrations (Council of Europe, 2024).

In 2021, one of every five prisoners are in pre-trial detention in Europe, making the median rate of 21.6% of pre-trial detainees in all European prisons. In Croatia, in 2021, 36.3% (1,281) of total prisoners (3,531) were not serving a final sentence in penitentiary institutions (See Figure 1.). Moreover, one in four of detainees in Greece were detained for longer than one year with pre-trial detention being used as an advance on the sentence (Morfonios, 2022).

Figure 1 Percentage of pre-trial detainees compared to all prison population

1.2 Alternative measures in Consortium states

At this time, **Poland** provides the following alternatives (often used in combination):

- Property guaranty (bail); a social guarantee;
- Guarantee of a trustworthy person;
- Police supervision or supervision of the superior in a military service;
- Order to leave premises;
- Suspension in the execution of duties, restraining order;
- Ban on contacting and publishing order concerning a member of the medical staff or persons to assist them and prohibition to leave the country (Article 266 PCPC).

The alternative measures that exist in **Greece** are as follows:

- Bail;
- Reporting before the investigating police authority;
- Prohibition to leave or access specific place or exit ban from the country;
- Prohibition to meet or associate with specific persons; and
- Restriction at home with electronic surveillance (Article 286 GCPC).

In **Croatia**, the Criminal Procedure Code (CCPC) allows for these alternatives to PTD:

- Release on bail;
- House arrest; and
- Precautionary measures.

The precautionary measures include:

1. Prohibition to leave the residence;
2. Prohibition to leave a certain place or area;
3. The obligation of the defendant to report regularly to a certain person or state body;
4. Prohibition of approaching a certain person, prohibition of establishing or maintaining a relationship with a certain person;
5. Prohibition to engage in a certain business activity, temporary seizure of a passport and other documents which serve to cross the state border;
6. Temporary revocation of a license to drive a motor vehicle;
7. Prohibition of stalking or harassment of the victim or another person;
8. Removal from home, internet access ban (Article 98 CCPC).

Types and most frequently applied alternatives to custody in **Bulgaria** are:

- Mandatory reporting to the police – reporting any change of address (most often applied in countries with good cooperation between the police and the judiciary);
- House arrest (more often without technical supervision);
- Bail; (BCPC)

The **Slovak** Criminal Procedure Code (SCPC) limits the range of cases for applying pre-trial detention (Article 71 SCPC). Article 80 and Article 81 of the SCPC stipulate cases in which the accused may be released pending trial and set out the alternatives to pre-trial detention, which include:

- Replacement of pre-trial detention by a guarantee of a trustworthy person or an interest association of citizens;
- A written promise of the accused;
- Replacement under the supervision of a probation and mediation officer; or a
- Financial guarantee (bail, deposit).

1.3 The Effects of Pre-trial Detention on Mental Health

Pre-trial detention is one of the leading causes of suicide. In Europe, there were 17.5 suicides per 10,000 people in pre-trial detention, while the proportion was 8.54 deaths in the rest of the prison population. The Czech Republic has the highest count in the EU with 51 suicides, while Slovakia counts almost 19 suicides of detainees per 10,000 people in pre-trial detention. The World Health Organization (WHO) warns how the first few hours and days are the most critical when it comes to detainees taking their own life. Suicide prevention is yet to have a cohesive and concrete program to be implemented in detention centres (Bernardo et al., 2022). The WHO also noted how suicide rates of pre-trial detainees are three times higher than those of convicted prisoners. The disproportion of pre-trial detention remains evident in significantly affecting people with low socio-economic status; the inability to make bail, loss of employment etc. (Schönteich, 2013).

2 Development of Proposed Solutions

This Policy brief is in part a result of a desk research conducted within the RELEASE project. The main objective of the RELEASE project is to contribute to the coherent application of EU laws across the consortium states and to promote judicial cooperation in criminal matters. The project aims at facilitating the establishment of mutual trust amongst the target groups and improvement of the national justice systems. In particular, the RELEASE project focuses on the pre-trial detention requirements and their implementation, supporting the effectiveness of the enforced decisions on the matter and the establishment of a united European approach. Consortium states within the project include Bulgaria, Slovakia, Croatia, Greece and Poland.

The desk research in question provides an overview of the national legal framework, literature review and case law analysis. It is based on the general data collection, and statistics. By combining the national legal framework of each consortium state, literature review and case law analysis the desk research offers a comprehensive overview of the current state of play in each consortium state.

Having said that, the main arguments that this Policy brief focuses on are as follows:

1. The use of PTD disproportionately impacts persons belonging to vulnerable and marginalized groups and damages human rights;
2. Significant overuse of PTD negatively impacts national criminal justice systems and undermines the rule of law at national level;

3. PTD should only be used as a measure of last resort as it was intended, and not as a punishment.

Main advantages of non-custodial restrictive measures (depending on the type of measure) include:

- The suspect stays with their family, maintains their social ties, doesn't lose employment;
- Lower costs of incarceration;
- Improving the work of the judiciary;
- Reduction of the prison population;
- Technical monitoring allows for observation of the individual at all times.

In case of detainees losing their connection to their family members, losing employment etc., the risk of reoffending is higher. During the COVID-19 pandemic, when penitentiary institutions were forced to reduce prison populations globally, success was found in countries (Portugal and Bahrain) with good practice examples when using non-custodial measures (Thailand Institute of Justice, 2022). While other countries showed higher rates of the prison population even during the pandemic bringing in question the rule of law in Europe (Fair Trials, 2021).

When it comes to pre-trial injustice, one of the leading causes is the judges' fear of media criticism, especially in cases where a heavy punishment is expected. This leads to their decisions being influenced by outside criticism and rushed without much factual evidence for prolonging custody. Being in custody makes it harder to gather evidence of one's innocence and circumstances. The over-crowdedness and less than sanitary conditions in penitentiary institutions pose a risk to the detainees as well as the correctional officers and prison staff. Furthermore, holding people in pre-trial detention implies significant additional costs in comparison to alternative and less restrictive measures. Detainees report being more likely to plead guilty when in pre-trial detention, even if they are innocent, because they are afraid of a longer sentence. They also feel forced to plead guilty by the police and/or prosecutors. On the other hand, judges fear the repercussions of releasing offenders, and their release resulting in reoffending in which case they feel like the blame falls on them. The overuse of pre-trial detention is one of the main causes of prison overcrowding globally. Considering the higher daily costs of imprisonment, alternative measures cause less economic harm as well (Heard & Fair, 2019).

During the workshops with judges, lawyers and legal practitioners, the following proposals emerged:

- Strict adherence to the principle of proportionality;
- Permanent, continuous and mandatory training of all justice officials in the light of continuous social and political changes;
- Critical treatment of the media's role in matters of justice;
- Activation and vigilance of audit mechanisms on persons and institutions that hinder the work of justice in this particular matter;
- Adoption and operation of modern technological means to facilitate alternative measures (electronic surveillance, geo-location);
- Permanent and effective surveillance of the accused in the implementation of alternative measures;
- Time limits need to be set on all alternative measures;
- Substantial activation of the judicial police, charged with the implementation of alternative measures.

2.1 Cost-effective means of implementation

Besides the significant impact on individuals giving rise to violation of some of their most basic human rights and fundamental freedoms, the available research shows that the overuse of pre-trial detention also carries significant additional costs, which are considerably higher than the alternatives, and hence can lead to further economic and social harm.

Average daily cost per detainee varies from a couple of Euros to almost 60 Euros. One of the lowest costs is in Bulgaria with 5.70 Euros, then a rapid increase of cost in Greece with 28 Euros, then Poland with 29.90 Euros, Croatia with 55.4 Euros, and lastly, the highest average daily cost per detainee is in Slovakia costing up to 56.60 euros (European Commission, 2022) (See Figure 2.).

Figure 2 Average daily cost per detainee (in Euros)

Average daily cost per detainee in Euros

Electronic monitoring has increased in use over the last few years, and has proven to be one of the more efficient alternatives to PTD. Bulgaria introduced house arrest with electronic tagging in 2019, and it resulted in 137 people avoiding custody. Using electronic monitoring as a measure would also better the overcrowding issues experienced throughout European prisons. Despite a variety of non-custodial measures being available, countries report its scarce use in practice (Croatia, Poland, and Slovakia). One of the causes of this is the judiciary's unawareness of these measures. Therefore, the issue of the existence of alternative measures is not the main cause of the overuse of PTD. Accordingly, further education on the possibility of a higher rate of the implementation of non-custodial measures is required (European Commission, 2022). The European Supervision Order (ESO) is also reported to be underused in all EU Member states with Spain issuing only seven of them between 2015-2020 (Venâncio et al., 2022). Moreover, bail makes it more likely that defendants will reappear in court, and with that reduce costs for the criminal justice system (Liu, Nunn & Shambaugh, 2018).

3 Policy recommendations for Consortium states

3.1 Poland

Although Poland ranks fairly low on the list of countries that use pre-trial detention regularly, year after year, the number of people facing PTD is increasing. According to Polish legislation, the principle should be the use of PTD when other preventive (non-custodial) measures do not suffice. In practice, this principle seems to have been reversed - the use of pre-trial detention is considered first, and only then, it is analyzed whether non-custodial measures

will suffice after all. Legislative committees should therefore seek to introduce such regulations that will encourage prosecutors and judges to use non-custodial preventive measures.

During project events, Polish stakeholders indicated that consideration should be given to expanding the catalogue of non-custodial preventive measures, such as, for example:

- A ban on leaving the Schengen zone;
- The introduction of an electronic surveillance system through which law enforcement would monitor the person's whereabouts.

The latter measure has been introduced in the past, but after a few months, due to political changes, it was removed and its effectiveness could not really be tested. There was also a discussion among stakeholders about the prerequisites behind pre-trial detention measures. Most discussed were:

- The validity of the premise of a severe threatened punishment as a stand-alone basis for the use of this isolation measure;
- The amount of time the parties have until the court session at which it will decide whether to use pre-trial detention.

3.2 Greece

It is understood that in order to fulfil the goal of this brief, that is to ensure the appearance of the accused in the trial and their submission to the sentence that may be imposed on the defendant, the Court should not resort to the "easy" solution of temporary detention. However, in order for it to work systematically not only in finding alternative measures but also mainly in establishing the effective application of these measures in the legal system, with the dominant support of these measures from the political system, alternatives must be strengthened with proper surveillance, so that they become effective. Therefore, they can be imposed on those who do not have a known residence in the country (foreigners, immigrants), so that they become a realistic option for other categories of persons. The imposition of alternative measures can also be strengthened if the State bears their costs, so that lower socio-economic social groups can also join.

In Greece, non-custodial measures are extensively used, but not respected. In case of PTD, the detainee has the right to request the substitution of the pre-trial detention or restrictive order upon the completion of a definite period.

Some improvements could be made in the legislative framework for the implementation of good practices through the unification of standards. It is crucial to have access to infrastructure and professional services of judges to assess any risk in supporting these measures. Furthermore, practical training for Investigators in accordance with the rules of the ECtHR and International Treaties is important.

In any case, the monitoring and training of judges and prosecutors in the application of PTD and alternative measures through good practices are deemed necessary and will be beneficial. The exchange of good practices facilitates the decision-making process. The international cooperation and the exchange of good practices have a beneficial effect in the field of Justice in Greece.

Furthermore, to enhance the use of the alternative measures the following points should be taken into consideration:

- More effective co-operation between judicial, social and Law-enforcement authorities;
- Improvement of means of electronic surveillance, such as to reduce the cost, to provide geo-location etc.;
- Exchange of knowledge and procedures between other jurisdictions;
- Conduction of trainings and workshops regarding the use of alternative measures and the negative effects of the pre-trial detention;
- Introduction of a new body/authority responsible to ensure the sound and proper application of the imposed measure;
- Release of an official statistical list every 3, maximum 6 months, regarding the number of pre-trial detainees in the country.

3.3 Croatia

Although Croatian legislation has many electronic monitors (over 100 electronic monitors) at their disposal, judges claim that only a couple have been put to use in order to prevent custody in the past year. Moreover, since judges within this project events stated how they feel pressured to subject defendants to PTD in public sensitive media cases, raising awareness through the media would improve the practice of using pre-trial detention as a preventative measure. It is also imperative to address the over-crowdedness of Croatian prisons, with Osijek being at 205% capacity, followed closely by Karlovac with 170% capacity. This amount of overpopulation in penitentiary institutions is not providing adequate working conditions for correctional officers and the rest of the prison staff, as well as the detainees themselves. Furthermore, since being detained prevents people from collecting all the necessary evidence for their case, all while feeling pressured to plead guilty, the judiciary should be warned of

inadequate practice during trial as a result of this. There should be consistent training of judges, lawyers and legal practitioners on the implementation of alternatives and the benefits it would bring to the criminal justice system as a whole. They must also be made aware of the mental health issues and risks that detainees face during the first few days in detention. Additionally, being informed on good practice examples of alternative measures being successful on a global level is possible with more EU Member State cooperation such as achieved by this project.

EC's Recommendations from 2022 clarify that detainees must be treated with respect and dignity, especially in term of the prohibition of torture and inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment as laid down in Article 3 of the European Convention on Human Rights and Article 4 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Member states should review the reason for custody in intervals of maximum 1 month.

Some of the possible measures include:

- Undertakings to appear before a judicial authority as and when required, not to interfere with the course of justice and not to engage in particular conduct, including that involved in a profession or particular employment;
- Requirements to report on a daily or periodic basis to a judicial authority, the police or other authority;
- Requirements to accept supervision by an agency appointed by the judicial authority;
- Requirements to submit to electronic monitoring;
- Requirements to reside at a specified address, with or without conditions as to the hours to be spent there;
- Requirements not to leave or enter specified places or districts without authorization;
- Requirements not to meet specified persons without authorization;
- Requirements to surrender passports or other identification papers; and
- Requirements to provide or secure financial or other forms of guarantees as to conduct pending trial (European Commission, 2022).

3.4 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, the majority of legal practitioners recognizes that the array of negative consequences for the detainee and their relatives are often ignored. Lawyers and judiciary agree that detention is contrary to the presumption of innocence and should be applied restrictively, only for serious crime and or/ exceptional circumstances. Media and public opinion pressure on the Court and the risk of ineffectiveness of alternative pre-trial measures are seen as the main reasons for the overuse of detention.

One way to limit the application of this most severe measure is to collect additional information about the suspect beyond that collected by the police during the investigation when deciding on any pre-trial restriction measure assignment. Moreover, information about previous offences and convictions, as well as information about the person's work and family status, incl. the dependence of family members on them, living conditions, their state of health should be always sought. A comprehensive assessment of the information needs to be made, both in terms of the risk of continued criminality or absconding and the potential impact of detention on the person and/or their family. This should be reminded to the prosecution as they have the obligation to collect both inculpatory and exculpatory evidence, while the defence lawyer (both if employed by the accused or assigned to the latter pursuant legal aid) should be adamant about presenting this information to the Court during the pre-trial measure hearing.

The European Surveillance Order which was introduced by the Council Framework Decision of 2009 for the application between the Member States of the European Union of the principle of mutual recognition to acts of imposing procedural coercion measures as an alternative to preliminary detention is a tool to avoid or shorten the period of detention, allowing the accused to await trial in their country of residence and equal treatment of foreigners and other citizens. Yet this tool is widely unknown by the legal practitioners rendering it ineffective in practice. To this end, more structural efforts (awareness raising, training and mutual learning activities at cross-border level) should be invested in order not only to diminish the use of the pre-trial detention in cross-border cases but also to enhance the mutual trust among EU Member States.

Expanding the application of alternatives to detention in the pre-trial criminal proceedings may be accomplished by:

- Selection of an appropriate measure for each specific case;
- Gathering more information about the accused (their personality, social environment, etc.) to make an informed decision;
- Providing a well-founded explanation why an alternative measure was not applied in the Court decision;
- Scientific analysis of the effectiveness of existing alternatives and risk assessment methodologies establishment;
- For minor crimes, alternatives should be applied as a rule;
- Training of practitioners on the existing alternatives and how to apply them;
- Regular publication in media of successful examples of alternative measures application in pre-trial criminal proceedings from the practice;

- Introduction of additional alternative measures (obligation to spend specified hours in a dedicated location, restriction of mobility, not to commit a crime of a voluntary nature, calling the respective competent authority in a specified interval etc.) in the Bulgarian Criminal Procedure Code empowering the Court to assign them either individually or cumulatively (e.g. to combine bail with restriction of mobility and limit of contact with certain persons) to ensure the presence of the accused in the trial.

3.5 Slovakia

In Slovakia's case, the project activities carried out so far - be it the responses of the target group of judges, prosecutors, lawyers and criminal judges to the questionnaires or the mutual learning activities - national workshops - have shown that there is a consensus among the target group on the importance of increasing the use of alternatives to PTD. However, there is also agreement among the target group that there are significant practical shortcomings that severely limit the use of alternatives on a larger scale. These are not legislative shortcomings, but rather purely practical-technical ones which in fact prevent the use of alternatives. From the point of view of judges and prosecutors, in many cases, it is not a matter of reluctance or categorical refusal to impose alternatives, but rather of considering the practical constraints that limit their usability.

In many cases, judges resort to the use of pre-trial detention not because they consider it necessary or the most appropriate, but because of the practical shortcomings of the imposition and implementation of alternatives in the conditions of the Slovak Republic.

The responses to the questionnaire showed that in Slovakia the target group perceives bail and supervision of the defendant by a probation and mediation officer as the most effective alternative to PTD.

4 Conclusion

As seen in policy recommendations, Bulgaria, Poland, Greece, Slovakia and Croatia require similar courses of action in the way that they have most of the same alternative measures available and have the same problem of not implementing them.

It is necessary to build trust in alternatives on the part of not only judges and prosecutors, but also to build society's trust in these tools, which could lead to greater demand for their use on the part of society. In order for that objective to be successful, strengthening the practical usability and functionality of the alternatives is necessary. There is a solid start for an increased use of alternative measures in practice considering the existing list of

alternatives, but more advanced training of the judiciary should be mandatory. By conducting this project, it has become apparent that there is a significant space for change and improvement, and that both the judiciary and lawyers are open to further education and cooperation. Furthermore, cooperation between EU MS's would be a ground-breaking venture, which has been pointed out by the judiciary and lawyers alike. This would include a more comprehensive program of alternative measures implemented on a European level.

In order to ensure functionality of the alternatives, in addition to a significant increase in human resources, technical support is required and, ideally, a review of the existing alternatives based on the results of the evaluation of their effectiveness. As the reasons for the insufficient use of alternatives to pre-trial detention lie in specific practical shortcomings, it is necessary to focus primarily on these. Adequate funding and staffing are therefore a prerequisite for greater use of alternatives to pre-trial detention. This must be followed by training for the relevant legal professions - judges and prosecutors. Inadequate staffing of probation officers and mediators has a direct impact on the low imposition of alternatives, as it makes it virtually impossible.

On the other hand, it is hard to ignore the influence of the media and the public in demanding the use of PTD in politically and socially sensitive cases. Therefore, it would certainly be beneficial to aim at educating the wider public and journalists in this sense.

Changes should also be made to the legal provisions that form the basis for the use of pre-trial detention, as well as to the provisions relating to the proceedings until the trial phase of the criminal proceedings. Policy makers' attention should also be drawn to the need for changes in funding for preventive measures. This is not only about increasing the number of employees and devices available in the criminal process, but also about increasing financial expenditure on training among practitioners, which would build awareness of the use of preventive measures.

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